

KT4D

Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

KT4D Social Risk Toolkit Module A: AI, free will and autonomy – Individuals' autonomy in their online choices

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Deliverable Abstract

The integration of artificial intelligence in multiple aspects of our daily lives poses a great challenge in shaping civic participation within societies. Effective civic engagement finds its foundation in the empowerment of citizens who actively participate in public discourse, and in the articulation of their viewpoints. Understanding the dynamics that underpin trust in democratic institutions in this new context is thus important.

Module A questions individuals' capacity to navigate AI-based content and recommendations while safeguarding their autonomy and free will. Module B examines the requisites for the utilisation of AI to preserve institutional trust. Indeed, the use of AI in a wide range of fields could generate situations that are, or are perceived to be, unfair, thereby threatening the social balance established between members of the same community. Module C puts the new challenges posed by technological transformations into perspective, by analysing historical precedents and how they have shaped culture and social interactions over centuries.

Through a comprehensive exploration and assessment, modules A, B and C of KT4D's Social Risk Toolkit will seek to address an important challenge: identify exactly where regulation is needed to ensure that AI benefits society as a whole, and identify the conditions for trust in social institutions, in order to guarantee effective public debate and societal choices are made by citizens themselves.

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Individuals' autonomy in their online choices

Navigating online environments involves a continuous stream of small decisions: whether to click, scroll, watch, share, ignore, or disengage. Individually, these choices appear trivial; cumulatively, they shape how attention is allocated, how time is spent, and how preferences and attitudes are reinforced. The sense of autonomy at stake in digital environments does not primarily concern spectacular acts of persuasion, but the ordinary ability to steer one's actions in line with one's intentions over time.

This chapter examines autonomy as a form of agentic control grounded in attention regulation, goal-directed action, and reflexivity. It explores how algorithmic curation, interface design, and AI-driven personalisation structure the space of possible actions, sometimes facilitating choice and sometimes constraining it. Rather than treating autonomy as an all-or-nothing property, the analysis focuses on the conditions under which digital environments support or undermine individuals' capacity to remain authors of their own online behaviour.

1. How do algorithms influence people's choices?

1.1. Attentional mechanisms

A first consideration is the distinction between types of attention. William James (1890) originally used the concept of effort to differentiate between voluntary and involuntary attention. However, contemporary terminology more commonly distinguishes between endogenous attention, which is internally generated by an individual's will, and exogenous attention, which is triggered by external stimuli, such as a pop-up notification that suddenly captures one's focus.

The ability to focus our attention depends on a whole network of brain areas. This means that attentional failures are less due to faulty mechanisms filtering perceptual information than to a lack of stabilisation of the attentional system operated by executive control. This kind of failure can happen when we do not set ourselves a clear and well-motivated goal for the action we are about to carry out. Conversely, **the clearer we define our goal (and the stronger our motivation to achieve it), the easier it is to sustain our attention.** As shown by the work of Di Bello et al. (2022) executive control is achieved by connecting together the prefrontal and parietal cortex and by locking this network into priority processing of relevant information. Deliberation and decision-making directed towards clear, defined goals thus need to be facilitated.

Recent research in neuroscience has also contributed to unravelling the temporal dimension of attentional mechanisms, which can operate several times a second (Petitmengin & Lachaux, 2013). An example of such a mechanism is the pre-attentive filtering of information. The use of emotionally charged stimuli in advertisements or notifications increases the automatic power of attraction that they have on our attention. **The only way to deal with such captivating exogenous stimuli is to rely on automatism that are even more powerful and deeply anchored through the building of habits.**

Now, social networks can be described as systems designed to capture users' attention, which is then sold to advertisers through increasingly personalised and manipulative targeting strategies. An emerging perspective on understanding how social networks and digital applications capture attention involves **comparing these strategies to those used by casinos, the tobacco industry, or the food industry with sugary products**, as discussed by Natasha Schüll (2012). These tactics draw directly

from psychological research, including the principle of maintaining a certain degree of unpredictability in the delivery of rewards.¹

1.2. The role of design, the issue of addiction, and dark pattern techniques

Research analysing platforms through the lens of addiction and compulsion raises broader questions about the role of interface design, commonly referred to as **choice architecture**. Choice architecture is defined as the external environment in which individuals make decisions. A foundational concept in this field is the notion of *affordance*, which was developed by the psychologist James Gibson in the 1970s. Affordances refer to the properties of objects that naturally suggest their intended use. This concept has been crucial in the design of digital interfaces, focusing on the importance of creating interactions that are intuitive and obvious.

The integration of users' cognitive characteristics in the design process later expanded on this idea. This ecological approach consists in developing solutions that facilitate easy recognition of the actions required, promoting ease of use, ergonomic interfaces, and user-centred design. The aim is to design systems that are self-evident and minimise the cognitive effort required from users. However, the same approach can also lead to manipulation. The lack of friction in users' interactions with the system enables them to perform tasks with minimal attention, potentially releasing extra cognitive resources. At the same time, the quasi-automatic nature of these interactions reduces voluntary control and diminishes awareness of one's actions. This may result in increased time spent on certain activities or engagement in non-reflective behaviours. Thus, **while affordances can simplify and streamline user interaction, they can also encourage actions that occur with limited awareness or intentionality.**

Some platforms even rely on manipulative techniques like **dark patterns**, which are interfaces deliberately designed to deceive or manipulate users (Fitton & Read, 2019) by preventing users from exercising their autonomy. Some media have for example adopted a 'click-bait' model, offering headlines that optimise their appeal, regardless of the actual relevance of the content to the user (with headlines such as "9 Out Of 10 Americans Are Completely Wrong About This Mind-Blowing Fact"). Such titles exploit a basic emotional language and arouse curiosity but do not provide enough information without clicking on them. In fact, the stories do not need to be particularly attractive themselves, as long as users are tempted to click on the link.

Dark patterns are tested on thousands of subjects to determine which parameters are most effective. As Adam Alter (2017) says in his book *Irresistible: The rise of addictive technology and the business of keeping us hooked*, "In 2004 Facebook was fun, in 2016 it's addictive". The combination of infinite scrolling and personalised recommendations creates an immersive experience that is similar to a tunnel, inducing a state of absorption and heightened concentration. The intensified perception of control further contributes to the difficulty of disengagement, and exiting the application demands a substantial effort and considerable motivation. These effects are all the more pervasive as the user lacks visual cues: like in the experiment by Wansink, Painter & North (2005) where the use of self-refilling soup bowls altered the feeling of satiety, users of platforms such as TikTok or Instagram no longer feel the need to get out of the tunnel.

¹ Zatorre & Salimpoor (2013) used brain imaging to study the effects of different types of music on brain activity. It appears that the brain activities linked to the sensation of pleasure are triggered not only by the familiarity and predictability of a piece of music, but also, to some extent, by surprise and variability.

Some of the challenges of the digital environment include the erosion of autonomy due to manipulative choice architectures, distraction and cognitive overload (Kozyreva et al., 2020). With such precise information on our behaviour, preferences, and attitudes, recommendation systems can recommend the 'right' product, the 'right' article, the 'right' video, at the 'right' time, etc. Algorithms are very effective at selecting content that consumers will perceive as pleasurable and addictive. Analysis of browsing data enables content to be proposed that is close to what users like, but sufficiently different for it to be new. The monetisation of user attention duration on digital platforms incentivises the deliberate curation of content aimed at capturing and prolonging user engagement. As we saw in the previous section, this strategy often involves the presentation of emotionally evocative, sensational, or highly captivating content to retain user interest, as certain content resonates more deeply with the human experience due to its relevance to fundamental aspects of life.

1.3. Are social networks addictive?

From a scientific point of view, addiction typically includes a compulsive desire, difficulties in controlling its use and, sometimes, a physical withdrawal syndrome. In the case of social media use, there is no physiological habituation. Social media use falls outside the scope of the DSM-V's recognition of behavioural addictions, limited to video games and gambling (see Box 1 "Are social networks threatening to psychological health?"). While not classified as a distinct pathology, social networking exhibits nonetheless addictive characteristics by exploiting vulnerabilities in the brain's reward system, a fundamental component of motivation (Sherman et al., 2016). Posting photos that generate numerous likes will trigger the release of dopamine. The strength of this reward, akin to compulsive behaviours observed in animal experiments and analogous to slot machines, intensifies with greater variability and randomness in the reward pattern. Strategies used to foster addiction encompass diverse techniques such as infinite scrolling, notifications, likes, targeted recommendations, etc. These strategies build on priority alerts for cognitive processing and encourage engagement at the expense of ongoing activities. In France, a report published a few years ago (Adès et al., 2019) suggested that **vulnerabilities should be distinguished according to age group and individual characteristics**, and emphasised the role of content as much as time spent on screens. Time spent in front of a screen alone is not necessarily a sign of an addictive process. Most of the time, digital activities tend to co-exist with other occupations, not replace them. In some cases, they even reinforce them. And the intensity of online exchanges is accompanied by greater face-to-face socialisation.

In recent years, online platforms have been showing increased recognition of the issues surrounding the algorithms used to maximise user engagement, and have committed to working on solutions to the problem of the problematic use of social media among the youth. For instance, in 2022, Instagram introduced a feature called 'take a break', as another measure to address user engagement and well-being, and in 2023 TikTok introduced a 60-minute time restriction for users under 18, which requires the user to enter a password to continue. Disabling push notifications has been made easier, and notifications are now deactivated after 9pm for users aged 13-15, and after 10pm for those aged 16-17.

Social networks and psychological health

While the mental health of young people is deteriorating worldwide, with increasing cases of depression, anxiety and mental disorders (Twenge et al., 2021), the PISA report notes that in almost all the countries studied, loneliness at school has increased. For many experts, social networks are to blame. Between 2009 and 2012, the main social media platforms have undergone radical change, taking on a more toxic dimension: Facebook introduced the 'Like' button, Twitter the 'Retweet' function, and news feeds became algorithmic, based on engagement. As a result, social networks have disrupted social interactions. In France, 1 child in 4 feels they spend too much time on their phone, according to a survey by the Heaven agency. Yet correlation is not causation, and many other potential factors are at play. Studies on the effects of time spent on social networks are many and contradictory. Some studies conclude that there is a clearly identified effect on mental health, others that there is a weak association, and others that there is no effect at all. A meta-analysis suggests that there is indeed a negative effect, but that it remains very weak (Masciantonio et al., 2023).

However, screen time may not be a good variable. Many factors are confounded in the same analysis, including factors with positive effects on well-being. For example, a Pew Research Center study conducted in 2022² shows that half of American teenagers born between 1995 and 2012 feel more accepted online than offline. Does active involvement in online exchanges determine the positive effects of social media? Some studies show that the more involved users are in content production, and the more they interact with other users, the less negative the effect on their mental health. In 2016, a study conducted in Quebec by Morin-Major et al. (2016) showed that the more friends adolescents had on Facebook, the higher their basal levels of cortisol, a hormone produced during stressful experiences. Conversely, the more photos and stories they exchanged, the lower the cortisol level, because the interactions were of better quality. However, other studies such as Beyens et al. (2020) do not find the same results.

The difficulty researchers have in finding consistent results stems from the fact that, more often than not, social networks are not studied per se, but screen time in general, and the population in general. For example, a study conducted by Orben & Przybylski (2019) on hundreds of thousands of British and American teenagers' data revealed a low association between digital technology use and adolescent well-being. But when these same data were analysed by considering only data corresponding to the use of social networks by young adolescent girls, this association was multiplied by four. Adolescent girls (especially between the ages of 11 and 13) are in fact on the front line: one solid finding is that exposure to idealised bodies has a negative impact on body image (Orben et al., 2024). Young girls who undergo social comparison on these platforms are at greater risk of developing psychological disorders (Kleemans et al., 2018). In conclusion, there are indeed links between social networks and mental health problems, but these depend very much on the individual and the context in which individuals are exposed, and on the characteristics of the platforms (for example, the positivity bias is stronger on Instagram, there are more messages associated with anger on X, there is only video content on TikTok, etc.). A better understanding of the combinations that turn out to be toxic, will enable regulation that is better adapted to the problems of the users themselves.

Box 1 – Social networks and psychological health

2. What does autonomy and freedom mean in this context?

Daily interactions with minor decisions, such as sharing content without fully engaging with it, participating in unintended controversies, or mindlessly scrolling through media, cumulatively exhaust our cognitive resources. This depletion impairs our capacity to engage in more substantial, introspective decision-making concerning our personal desires and identity.

² <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2022/11/16/connection-creativity-and-drama-teen-life-on-social-media-in-2022/>

2.1. Ability to decide what you want vs. Ability to do what you want to do

The ability to determine what we want differs from the capacity to act in pursuit of our goals. Philosopher Martha Nussbaum (2002) identifies **two essential aspects of empowerment**: first, the ability to adopt the role of an agent and **make decisions aligned with one's goals and values**; and second, the ability to **exercise one's agency effectively**, which involves executing decisions and converting intentions into concrete actions.

Autonomy of the will, that is, individuals' ability to decide for themselves the rules of behaviour they adopt, is an ideal that can never be attained. It is intrinsically unachievable because, as human beings, we are subject to physiological constraints beyond our control. Freedom, understood as the autonomy of the will, is therefore not an achievement whose preservation can be demanded, but a desirable horizon. In the late 1970's, the Belmont report³ had two convictions: the idea that individuals should be considered as autonomous agents (introducing the notion of informed consent); and also, the idea that vulnerable people should be given assistance and protection. However, these two notions are contradictory, as on the one hand, the individual is considered to be autonomous, and on the other hand, the patient is considered to be in a state of vulnerability (due to age or a particular condition).

2.2. Conditions of freedom

Freedom of choice can be achieved by combining reflexivity about one's choices with the regulation of attention and emotions. This approach is based on a Spinozist definition of freedom. For Spinoza, freedom is based on adequate knowledge of the causes that determine what we do. By understanding the stimuli that can trigger our behavioural automatisms, we can devise strategies to avoid them. As we deliberate, we question whether this influence is consistent with the goals we have set for ourselves. Our actions become free because we have checked their consistency with our goals before we act. Whether or not the world is ultimately determined has no incidence on our responsibility as social beings.⁴

This involves, on the one hand, developing the kinds of automatisms and habits that make us act spontaneously in ways that are consistent with who we want to be and what we think is right, and, on the other hand, developing a disposition that activates a more reflexive relationship with ourselves in certain situations, making us more capable of inhibiting unwanted automatic tendencies.

Willpower alone cannot be the key to freedom because it is exercised through both conscious and automatic actions, the analysis of their consequences, and deliberation. Rather, freedom consists in working on the formation of our own personality until we can effectively consider our spontaneous reactions in a given context as our own. **Automatisms that have not been submitted to reflexivity on the part of the user, and are not explicitly recognised as acceptable for the achievement of their goals, thus reduce our freedom.**

³ The Belmont Report is a foundational document in the field of research ethics, particularly in the context of research with human participants. It was published by the National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research in the United States in 1979.

⁴ <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/spinoza-psychological/>

3. How to promote reflexivity and metacognition

Discussion of the ethics of AI within experts' committees⁵ is set in a context where machines will most probably become increasingly efficient. One objective is thus to ensure that human beings do not risk abdicating their autonomy in favour of machines, and rather to empower individuals through technology. That said, as we saw in this module, it is interesting to think about alternative concepts of autonomy in the context of artificial intelligence, i.e. as the voluntary submission of individuals to the rules that they decide to prescribe for themselves, in accordance with their personal values, preferences and commitment. In this context, it becomes more a question of helping internet users to remain in a position to freely decide what they see, what they accept, what they want, etc.

Kozyreva et al. (2020) show the challenges posed by digital interfaces to human cognition, which undermines the well-being of individuals and the functioning of democratic societies. The only framework that can restore users' freedom is one that grants them **the power to inhibit their own automatisms and switch to deliberative mode**.⁶ Of course, not all the mechanisms of influence mentioned above necessarily alter people's autonomy. The judicious use of these same techniques can help us strengthen our power to act. Rather, it is about helping people to use these tools to achieve the goals they have set for themselves. Empowerment involves a better control of one's automatic behaviours, and more visibility on the intentions and mechanisms underlying the systems themselves. As people are naturally concerned about attempts to manipulate them (Sperber et al., 2010), if people know what to expect, they will naturally be more vigilant.

3.1. Building habits

Reflexivity, the ability to reflect on oneself, is an individual disposition. It also develops over the long term, through exchanges with others, the acquisition of knowledge, and the ability to stand back. Communities of experts, particularly scientific ones, are a good example.

Taking a step back and analysing one's own behaviour and thoughts is often necessary. This process is known as metacognition and involves asking questions such as *Are these automatisms right for me, and should I resist them?* Secondly, analysing the system we are interacting with is also important: questioning the designers' intentions, the interface's possibilities for action and configuration, etc. As many studies point out (Kozyreva et al., 2020), many features of social networks undermine the exercise of this reflexivity. Giving people more control is not enough if they are not prepared to exercise it. Traditional transparency measures, such as tools provided by platforms like Facebook's 'Why am I seeing this?' features are inadequate as they offer only superficial information and rely on active user engagement to be effective. And widespread acceptance of cookies by the majority may be more a result of limited alternatives than a conscious choice. Rather than empowering individuals, terms and conditions often demand the assent of users without providing any space for deliberation. Intricate language and extended document lengths can also contribute to creating an environment that lacks transparency and leaves users ultimately uninformed. Quite often then, giving users more possibilities is in fact a strategy for exploiting their consent and disguising collective disempowerment. While ostensibly free to navigate the Internet according to personal preferences, online choices made

⁵ E.g., the High Level Expert Group on AI (HLEG AI) set up by the European Commission, the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), and AI4People Institute.

⁶ There are, however, contexts in which the user follows selected automatisms, which have been deliberately selected for their effectiveness in achieving a certain goal.

by individuals often contradict the notion of a conscious and autonomous self. This is linked to the problem of alignment between the tool and the user: the goals of social networks and platforms (who want to make money and keep the latter's attention as much as possible) are not aligned with those of their users (who want to buy items or find information and maximise their well-being).

3.2. Training and education

Training and education are key to promoting reflexivity. Studies on 'dark patterns' have shown that consumers, even when they are aware of their existence, are not sufficiently equipped to avoid their manipulative effects. Information can only be effective if the user is able to understand it. Making internet users more autonomous can be partly achieved by increasing information literacy and cognitive resistance to manipulation. A valuable strategy for promoting autonomy in the context of social media usage involves the implementation of feedback mechanisms, such as tracking app usage time, setting alerts, and managing notifications. Such control tools can effectively mitigate excessive engagement, and they can also be incorporated into educational curricula, ensuring that individuals, particularly the youth, are equipped with the knowledge to navigate social networks responsibly.

Digital literacy and civic online reasoning

Digital literacy encompasses the knowledge and skills that the public needs to evaluate the quality of information coming from the media and to distinguish informational content from other types of content – for example, advertisements, opinion content or false information. One aim of researchers is to develop, especially in schools, an information culture, by exploring the media system, the relationships between journalists and other players in society, the role of citizens etc. (Tully et al., 2020; Vraga et al., 2022; Vraga & Tully, 2019). There is a wide range of literature on different ways of making people less vulnerable to misinformation through preventive interventions. The effects of interventions based on the use of red flags for unverified or debunked information (Clayton et al., 2020), on crowd wisdom (Allen et al., 2021; Martel et al., 2024) or on attention-priming techniques (Pennycook et al., 2021), have recently been explored. Researchers' attention has turned in particular to the dissemination of false information on social networks, adapting interventions such as inoculation to these changing environments. Inoculation is a technique introduced by McGuire (Compton, 2024) and inspired by vaccination, which consists of presenting a poorly argued claim on a subject in order to disqualify any future better-defended argument (Lewandowsky & van der Linden, 2021). It even seems to work in modifying already entrenched opinions. Based on this theory Roozenbeek & Van der Linden (2019) developed a game on the topic of fake news. The aim was to make people immune to fake news by putting them in the shoes of a disinformation agent. Fake news seems somewhat less reliable to the participants after they have played the game on social networks. Another approach called civic online reasoning has proved to be effective in improving the ability of high school and university students to detect dubious information, particularly on social networks (Wineburg et al., 2021). This approach is based on learning professional fact-checking techniques and is meant to be effective even in cases where disinformation is difficult to detect at first sight. However, such a strategy may fall short in cases where the problem lies in a lower motivation to know the truth on a given issue.

Box 2 – Digital literacy and civic online reasoning

Simple rules for information literacy can help users navigate and make sense of their social media feeds and other online information sources (see Box 2 "Digital literacy and civic online reasoning"). An experiment carried out in France is particularly instructive.⁷ It aimed to make a group of consumers aware of the effects of misleading or manipulative interfaces, and then to encourage the right

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https://www.modernisation.gouv.fr/files/2021-12/DGCCRF_%20rapport%20final_version%20finale_20.12.21_MC%20%28002%29.pdf

reflexes.⁸ The reputation lever could also be used (somewhat along the lines of the European Nutri-score⁹) to encourage users to leave a service they no longer endorse, by presenting a clear indication of how an operator respects certain criteria for example, in terms of design.

3.3. Interventions in information architectures

Reflexivity is not only the result of an individual and voluntary effort. **It also depends on external and environmental mechanisms.** This means adapting the digital space, its structure and the transparency of these mechanisms. Various interventions are possible :

Banning dark patterns

Some practices undermine users' autonomy by reducing their ability to make their own choices. Beyond personal data protection, sanctioning cognitive manipulation as such is now widely considered. This concerns techniques known as *bad nudge*, which encourage users to make decisions that run counter to their interests, or *bad sludge*, which prevent them from acting in their own interests by creating artificial difficulties that hinder their freedom of choice. But then comes the delicate question of what can be considered a manipulative or misleading interface (Mathur et al., 2021).¹⁰ Where does the difference lie between marketing and manipulation? The designer's job is precisely to guide the user towards uses or services that may suit them. The question is whether this manipulation is positive or negative, which is quite difficult because there are no objective indicators to assess it. To date, public authorities do not have sufficient knowledge to understand these mechanisms precisely and prove their effects.

Nudge techniques

Nudge techniques are behavioural interventions in choice architecture that influence behaviour in a predictable way and in the desired direction, for example via default settings. However, these techniques are criticised for raising ethical issues: 1. They typically influence behaviour unconsciously and automatically, without any epistemic cues allowing the user to deliberate before making a decision; 2. Assessing the good intentions of those who implement these nudges is difficult: how can one assess these intentions in the absence of any real evaluation of these public policies? (Chevallier & Perona, 2022). And what about the implementation of nudges by private entities such as the platforms themselves?

Boost techniques

Boost techniques are interventions designed to enhance users' cognitive and motivational skills, while preserving their decision-making autonomy. Typically, they can involve adding cues to the epistemic quality of information, or training people in simple rules of online reasoning. Different types of interventions have been explored to foster better online decision-making and resist manipulation. In one approach, individuals are inoculated against manipulation by enhancing their competence to detect such ads and make informed decisions. For instance, Lorenz-Spreen et al. (2021) showed that a short, simple intervention – prompting participants to reflect on their own personality – can

⁸ See also the work on psychological inoculation (Compton et al., 2021; Lewandowsky & van der Linden, 2021; Roozenbeek & van der Linden, 2019)

⁹ https://nutriscore-europe.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/NS_rapport-EU-V10_230202.pdf

¹⁰ Article 25 of the DSA on the definition of manipulated interfaces.

significantly increase people's ability to accurately identify ads that were targeted at them. Personal reflection and feedback significantly improved the ability to correctly identify targeted ads.

Cognitive science-inspired technological interventions in information architectures could, for example, involve the introduction of frictions (e.g., when accessing offensive content). A paradigm shift towards a techno-cognitive approach that fosters users' reflexive and deliberative abilities should be encouraged, giving preference to the 'boost' principle over the 'nudge' principle (Chammat & Giraud, 2019).

The references mentioned in this report are available in the Bibliography of KT4D Social Risk Toolkit Module A: AI, free will and autonomy. <https://zenodo.org/records/18374167>

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